

Effectiveness of Whatsapp as a Medical Teaching Learning Tool: A Comparative Study

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Abstract:

Background: WhatsApp is a popular instant messaging application which allows millions of people to keep in contact with each other and also helps anyone to create and publish content. It has the potential to influence the several domains of medical education.

Objectives: To assess the effectiveness of WhatsApp as a medical teaching learning tool in comparison with traditional lecture method and to assess the perception of medical students towards use of WhatsApp as a teaching learning tool.

Methodology: Students were divided into 2 groups and analysed for the effectiveness of WhatsApp as a teaching learning tool in comparison with lecture method. Perception of students towards use of WhatsApp as teaching learning tool was collected using validated feedback form.

Results: It was observed from the study that there was no statistically significant difference between use of WhatsApp and traditional lecture as a teaching learning tool. Majority of students perceived that WhatsApp helped to improve their enthusiasm in academics along with making difficult concepts simple and increased interaction between students and facilitator. High expectation of teacher's availability and group maintenance were most agreed challenges in use of WhatsApp as a teaching learning tool.

Conclusions: From the study finding we can conclude that use of WhatsApp as a teaching learning tool was equally effective as didactic lecture.

Keywords: WhatsApp, Teaching Learning Tool, Medical Education, Community Medicine.

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Introduction

Social media like WhatsApp has become an important part of modern life. It allows millions of people to keep in contact with each other and also helps anyone to create and publish content. [1] They facilitate sharing of various ideas and are being increasingly incorporated into healthcare and have the potential to influence the several domains of medical education.

Medical education has grown beyond the level of the classroom teaching, and social media like WhatsApp is seen as the bridge between informal and formal learning since it keeps students engaged with educational content even outside the classroom.

It allows them to communicate with their teachers and thereby it strengthens student-teacher relationship. [2] It also allows to show the creativity among the learners and presented new

dimension in medical education training strategies.[3] With the advent of smart phone, instant messaging applications are becoming a more popular communication tool for students compared to emails.

Several studies have found that use of mobile applications in education has been shown to increase student participation, enhance the feedback process and improve communication between student and tutor. [4]

As there are not many studies regarding the usefulness of WhatsApp as a teaching tool in medical education and knowing the effectiveness of using WhatsApp as a tool for teaching medical students will be beneficial for both teachers and students, this study was conducted with an objective to assess the effectiveness of WhatsApp

as a medical teaching learning tool in comparison with traditional lecture method.

Methodology

An Interventional study was conducted after getting clearance from institutional ethics committee during the period of January to March 2020 among second year MBBS students using universal sampling method. Students who gave consent for the study were included for the study. Overall, 80 students participated in the study.

Method of data collection: Consent for including in the study was obtained from all the participants, following which students who gave consent were given numbers according to their roll number and randomly divided into 2 groups i.e., group A and group B. Students in group A were added to WhatsApp group A and similarly Students in Group B were added to WhatsApp group B.

Two study modules were prepared containing important topics from community medicine. Module 1 had three topics from epidemiological study designs and Module 2 had three topics from non-communicable diseases. Students in Group A received the learning materials related to Module 1 through WhatsApp in the form of text messages, photos, video consisting of summary of class and documents including PowerPoint presentation and Students in Group B were taught the same topics through lecture method. Students in Group B received the learning materials related to Module 2 through WhatsApp in the form of text messages, photos, video consisting of summary of class and documents including PowerPoint presentation and

Students in Group A were taught the same topics through lecture method.

Both the groups were assessed at the end of 2 weeks, related to both the modules using Questionnaire consisting of objective type questions.

Perception of students regarding use of WhatsApp as a medical teaching tool was collected through the validated feedback form consisting of questions regarding the advantages and challenges of using WhatsApp as a teaching learning tool. [5]

The collected data was analysed by using descriptive statistics like mean, standard deviation and inferential statistics like Independent 't' test. Student's perception was assessed using Likert scale.

Results

Of the 80 students participated in the study, 40 students were part of WhatsApp group A and 40 students were part of WhatsApp group B. Among 80 students, 75 students who attended all the classes and assessment were included for final analysis.

It was observed from the study that for module 1, the mean score of students who were taught through WhatsApp (5.49) was lesser than those who were taught through lecture method (6.00) whereas for module 2, the mean score of students who were taught through WhatsApp (6.50) was slightly higher than those group of students who were taught through lecture method (6.44).

Table 1: Comparison of marks obtained by students in two different teaching learning tools according to learning module

S. No.	Module	Teaching learning tool	Mean (10)	SD	Unpaired t test
1	Module 1	Lecture	6.00	2.07	p=0.2723
		WhatsApp	5.49	1.94	t=1.1061
2	Module 2	Lecture	6.44	1.27	p=0.8223
		WhatsApp	6.50	1.18	t=0.2253

Table 2: Advantages of WhatsApp as a teaching learning tool

S.N.	Advantages	Agree	Neutral	Disagree
Technical advantages				
1	WhatsApp is easy to use	68(90.7%)	4(5.3%)	3(4%)
2	Freely available and downloadable	75(100%)	0(0%)	0(0%)
3	Provides privacy to the user	59(78.7%)	11(14.7%)	5(6.6%)
Educational and Instructional advantages to students				
1	Provide conducive environment	44(58.7%)	24(32%)	7(9.3%)
2	Improves enthusiasm	47(62.7%)	21(28%)	7(9.3%)
3	Makes difficult concepts simple	47(62.7%)	17(22.7%)	11(14.6%)
4	Easy accessibility to material	69(92%)	2(2.7%)	4(5.3%)
5	Facilitator's availability	60(80%)	15(20%)	0(0%)
6	Learning anytime anywhere	70(93.3%)	2(2.7%)	3(4%)

Table 3: Challenges faced by the learners on using WhatsApp as a teaching learning tool

S.N.	Challenges faced	Agree	Neutral	Disagree
Technical challenges				
1	Message flooding	18(24%)	40(53.3%)	17(22.7%)
2	Group maintenance	39(52%)	31(41.3%)	5(6.7%)
3	Eye strain	33(44%)	37(49.3%)	5(6.7%)
Educational and Instructional challenges				
1	High expectation of teacher's availability	35(46.7%)	29(38.7%)	11(14.6%)
2	Huge amount of learning material makes it confusing	17(22.7%)	37(49.3%)	21(28%)
3	Use of inappropriate language	0(0%)	32(42.7%)	43(57.3%)
4	No efforts by some students	36(48%)	21(28%)	18(24%)
5	Some students share material without actually learning	34(45.3%)	19(25.3%)	22(29.4%)

Discussion

From the study it was found that use of WhatsApp as a teaching learning tool was equally effective as didactic lecture since there was no significant difference observed between two teaching learning methods. Gon S et al., also in their study found that there was no significant difference between knowledge gained from didactic lectures and WhatsApp in teaching pathology. [5]

Most of the other studies involving WhatsApp as a teaching learning tool had used WhatsApp based teaching as a supplement to didactic lecture. Dyavarishetty PV et al., in their interventional study to test the effectiveness of WhatsApp in teaching community medicine observed that there was significant improvement in student's knowledge following teaching through WhatsApp. [6]

Similarly, studies conducted by Mohanakrishnan K et al. among medical students noticed that WhatsApp intervention has produced higher performance level than using didactic lectures alone. [7] Indu M et al., also found that there was significant improvement in the mean score of students who received learning materials through WhatsApp in supplementation to the conventional learning methods. [8]

Majority of students in this study agreed that WhatsApp is simple to use, easily available and downloadable and provides privacy to the user. Majority of students also perceived that WhatsApp helped to improve their enthusiasm in academics along with making difficult concepts simple and increased interaction between students and facilitator. High expectation of teacher's availability and group maintenance were most agreed challenges in use of WhatsApp as a teaching learning tool.

In a study done by Gon S et al., most of the students agreed that WhatsApp is simple to use and easily available and downloadable but majority of students disagreed that it is free of charge. Interaction between students, sharing of learning materials, easy accessibility to learning material,

high Interaction with facilitator and doubts immediately cleared were the other educational advantages with majority of students agreeing to it. Message flooding, time consuming and eye strain were common disadvantages observed in their study. [5]

Conclusions

From the study finding we can conclude that use of WhatsApp as a teaching learning tool was equally effective as didactic lecture since there was no significant difference observed between two teaching learning methods. Constant availability of facilitator and learning anytime and anywhere makes WhatsApp a convenient tool for teaching learning activity. Using WhatsApp as a supplement to lecture could further improve the academic performance of the students.

Limitations: The study population included only current second year students in one medical college, hence it cannot be generalized to the entire group of medical students and also the experience and personality of the faculty might have influenced students in the group of students taught through lecture method.

Recommendations: Innovative teaching learning methods and tools should be incorporated to medical education to overcome the problems faced in the changing scenario in medical education. E learning / M learning should be included as a teaching learning tool in undergraduate medical education, it will be useful especially useful during certain scenarios, when large gathering of students is preferably avoided. Implementation of WhatsApp based learning can overcome shortage of time. Further studies should be conducted involving larger population and other departments in different phases of MBBS course.

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